

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE***

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF GLAUCOMATOUS OPTIC NEUROPATHY AND TRAUMATIC OPTIC NEUROPATHY**Mirbabaeva F.A.**

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Resume. Relevance. The main significance of vision loss and optic nerve atrophy in traumatic optic neuropathy (TON) and glaucomatous optic neuropathy (GON), the cause is attributed to vascular changes in the blood supply to the optic nerve and retina. **Purpose of the study.** To determine the effectiveness of complex neuroprotective treatment of patients with GON and TON based on functional and hemodynamic parameters. **Material and methods.** We examined 22 patients (33 eyes) diagnosed with primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) with compensated intraocular pressure (IOP) and 20 patients (20 eyes) previously operated on for various midface bone fractures (MFBF) complicated by TON. **Complex treatment included:** Ethyl methylhydroxypyridinesuccinate 50 mg (Mexidol dissolved in 100 ml of 0.9% sodium chloride solution) intravenously by drip for 10 days, Lyophilisate 10 mg - 2.0 ml (Cortexin dissolved in 0.5 ml of 0.5% Novocaine solution) in a dose of 0.5 ml, which was administered parabolbarly for 10 days. **Results and conclusion.** The proposed regimen of drug prevention of TON and GON leads to persistent preservation of visual functions and improvement of hemodynamic parameters (83%).

Key words: glaucomatous optic neuropathy, traumatic optic neuropathy, neuroprotection, Mexidol, microcirculation

ГЛАУКОМАЛИ ОПТИК НЕЙРОПАТИЯ ВА ТРАВМАТИК ОПТИК НЕЙРОПАТИЯНИ КОМПЛЕКС ДАВОЛАШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ СОЛИШТИРМА ТАХЛИЛИ**Мирбабаева Ф.А.**

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Резюме. Долзарблиги. Глаукомали оптик нейропатия (ГОН) ва травматик оптик нейропатия (ТОН) да кўриш ўткирлигини пасайиши ва кўрув нервини атрофиясига олиб келувчи асосий сабаб бўлиб тўр парда ва кўрув нервнинг қон билан таъминланишини бузилиши хисобланади. Тадқиқот мақсади. ГОН ва ТОНли беморларда нейропротекторлар билан даволашни функционал ва гемодинамик кўрсаткичлар асосида тахлил қилиши. **Материал ва услублар.** Биз компенсацияланган кўз ичи босими (КИБ)ли бирламчи очиқ бурчакли глаукома (БОБГ) таъхиси қўйилган 22 бемор (33 кўз) ва юз ўрта соҳаси суюқларининг синиши билан амалиёт ўтказган ва кейинчалик ТОН билан асоратланган 20 нафар бемор (20 кўз)ни текширувга олдик. **Комплекс даво қуйидагиларни ўз ичига олган:** Этилметилгидроксипиридинасуцинат 50 мг (Мексидол 100 мл 0,9% ли натрий хлорид эритмасида эритилди) вена ичига 10 кун давомида томчилаб юборилди, Лиофилизат 10 мг – 2,0 ml (Cortexin 0,5% ли Новокаин эритмасида эритилди) 0,5 мл, эритмани 10 кун парабубар давомида юборилди. **Натижа ва хулоса.** ТОН ва ГОНни даволаш учун тавсия этилган медикаментоз даво чоралари кўрув функцияларини узоқ сақланишига, гемодинамик кўрсаткичларни (83%) яхшиланишига олиб келди.

Калит сўзлар: глаукомали оптик нейропатия, травматик оптик нейропатия, нейропротекция, Мексидол, микроциркуляция

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ КОМПЛЕКСНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ГЛАУКОМНОЙ ОПТИЧЕСКОЙ НЕЙРОПАТИИ И ТРАВМАТИЧЕСКОЙ ОПТИЧЕСКОЙ НЕЙРОПАТИИ**Мирбабаева Ф.А.**

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Резюме. Актуальность. Основное значение снижения зрения и атрофии зрительного нерва при травматической оптической нейропатии (ТОН) и глаукомной оптической нейропатии (ГОН) отводятся сосудистым изменениям в системе кровоснабжения зрительного нерва и сетчатки. **Цель исследования.** Определить эффективность комплексного нейропротекторного лечения пациентов с ГОН и ТОН на основании функциональных и гемодинамических показателей. **Материал и методы.** Нами было обследовано 22 больных (33 глаза) с диагнозом первичная открытоугольная глаукома (ПОУГ) с компенсированным внутриглазным давлением (ВГД) и 20 пациентов (20 глаз) ранее оперированными

с различными переломами костей средней зоны лица (СЗЛ), осложнившиеся ТОН. Комплексное лечение включало: Этилметилгидроксипиридинасуцинат 50 мг (Мексидол растворяют в 100 мл – 0,9% раствора натрия хлорида) внутривенно капельно в течение 10 дней, Лиофилизат 10 мг – 2,0 мл (Cortexini растворяли в 0,5 мл 0,5% растворе Новокаина) в дозе 0,5 мл, который вводили парабульбарно в течение 10 дней. Результаты и заключение. Предлагаемая схема медикаментозной профилактики ТОН и ГОН приводит к стойкому сохранению зрительных функций, улучшению гемодинамических показателей (83%).

Ключевые слова: глаукомная оптическая нейропатия, травматическая оптическая нейропатия, нейропротекция, Мексидол, микроциркуляция

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Relevance. The development of the pathological process of optic neuropathy (ON) of any type is based on ischemia and hypoxia of nerve fibers with a weakening of antioxidant activity, which may be preceded by circulatory impairment, compression of optic nerve fibers, blockade of axonal transport, intoxication, activation of peroxidation processes, and neurotoxic reactions. However, the intensity of these mechanisms, their location, and the sequence of their onset vary depending on the underlying pathological process. [13,12].

For example, in primary glaucoma, the main triggers for the development of optic neuropathy are increased intraocular pressure or decreased cerebrospinal fluid pressure in the retrobulbar optic nerve. This leads to deformation of the supporting structures (especially the lamina cribrosa of the sclera) with subsequent compression of nerve fiber bundles in the deformed canaliculi of the lamina cribrosa of the sclera and/or hypoxia of the optic nerve head, which leads to optic neuropathy [12,7].

Traumatic optic neuropathy (TON) is “a visual impairment resulting from direct or indirect damage to the optic nerve as a result of traumatic impact” [8].

According to the statistics department of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan and domestic authors, in the structure of primary disability, blindness and low vision, GON (40-42%) ranks first, and TON are in third place (16-18%) after age-related macular degeneration [1, 15, 14].

The vessels of the retina and optic nerve have the ability to autoregulate blood supply. A weakening of this ability is considered one of the risk factors for the development of gonadotropin-negative syndromes [16]. Among the causes of metabolic changes are hemocirculatory disorders leading to ischemia and hypoxia [4,12].

The main significance of vision loss and optic nerve atrophy in TON and GON, vascular changes in the blood supply system of the optic nerve and retina are attributed [3].

If in case of injuries to the zygomatic-orbital complex, changes in the normal hemodynamics of the orbital vessels reduce the trophism of the eye tissues and cause structural shifts and functional disorders [10, 14], then in glaucoma also a decrease in the initial values of hemodynamic parameters is one of the leading pathogenetic links of GON, which leads to hypoxia and the optic nerve and the inner parts of the retina (layer of ganglion cells and nerve fibers).

Of the medicinal products, the most widely used are antioxidant, vasodilator, nootropic drugs, NMDA receptor blockers, neuropeptides, and neuroprotectors [9].

And yet, one of the most promising directions in the treatment of optic neuropathies of glaucoma and traumatic etiology is the development and transition to complex drug treatment, including the use of neurotropic drugs that are able to penetrate into nerve fibers in small doses and improve the processes of axonal transport of neurons [11,12,5,6].

In this regard, the search for new research aimed at early detection, development of diagnostic algorithms and treatment of optic neuropathy regardless of etiology, prevention of the onset of disability and complete loss of vision is highly relevant and justified.

Currently, standards for the comprehensive treatment of optic neuropathy are being developed that promote neuroprotection of the retina and optic nerve by enhancing the processes of axonal transport of neurons.

The aim of the study was to determine the effectiveness of complex neuroprotective treatment for patients with GON and TON based on functional and hemodynamic parameters.

Materials and methods. To achieve the set goal, we examined 22 patients (33 eyes) with a diagnosis of POAG with compensated IOP, including 12 women and 10 men aged from 39 to 75 years and 20 patients (20 eyes) previously operated on for various fractures of the midface bones (MFB), which were subsequently identified as TON. The patients' ages ranged from 19 to 45 years (average age 32 ± 4): 32 were men (91,4%) and 3 were women (8,5%). All patients were of working age.

The comprehensive examination included: general ophthalmological examination (visiometry, tonometry, biomicroscopy, ophthalmoscopy, perimetry), as well as ophthalmic doppler ultrasound (ODU).

Patients were divided into two groups depending on the type of ON.

The first group consisted of 20 patients (20 eyes) who presented early. The day after reconstructive surgery, the ophthalmologist prescribed ethyl methylhydroxypyridinesuccinate in addition to the traditional conservative treatment. 50 mg (Mexidol dissolved in 100 ml of 0.9% sodium chloride solution) intravenously by drip for 10 days, Lyophilisate 10 mg – 2,0 ml (Cortexini dissolved in 0,5 ml of 0,5% Novocaine solution) in a dose of 0,5 ml, which was administered parabolbarly for 10 days .

The second group consisted of 22 patients (32 eyes) with GON whose IOP was normalized by medication or surgery. The average tonometric IOP was $21,2 \pm 1,8$ мм. Hg , the maximum IOP level was 23 мм. Hg. This group of patients also received ethyl methylhydroxypyridinesuccinate along with hypotensive epibulbar therapy. 50 mg (Mexidol dissolved in 100 ml of 0.9% sodium chloride solution) intravenously by drip for 10 days, Lyophilisate 10 mg – 2,0 ml (Cortexini dissolved in 0,5 ml of 0,5% Novocaine solution) in a dose of 0,5 ml, which was administered parabolbarly for 10 days .

The dynamics of treatment were monitored through 10 days, 1 and 3 months after the therapy.

The effectiveness of neuroprotective treatment in the examined patients was assessed using standard ophthalmological methods. Analysis of optic disc parameters and the thickness of the peripapillary retinal nerve fiber layer during treatment was performed using an OST Stratus optical coherence tomograph (version 3000) from Zeiss (Germany). To determine the hemodynamic characteristics of the ophthalmic artery, we used ophthalmic Doppler ultrasound (ODU). This consisted of determining the frequency shift between the ultrasound emitted and reflected from an object, proportional to the velocity of the object, with subsequent calculation of the velocity of the structures. Ophthalmic Doppler ultrasound in the ophthalmic artery basin was performed using a PHILIPSHD 11 XE expert-class ultrasound system using a linear transducer at an emission frequency of 4 and 8 MHz in continuous (or pulsed) mode.

Hemodynamic characteristics were determined in the ophthalmic artery (OA) in the section before the formation of its arch above the optic nerve, in the central retinal artery (CRA) no further than 10 mm from the posterior pole of the eyeball in close proximity to the optic nerve, in the posterior short ciliary arteries (PSCA) 0,7-0,33 mm from the posterior pole of the eyeball in close proximity to the optic nerve.

The average statistical values of blood flow velocity in the ophthalmic artery are normally: V_{syst} – from 32,7 cm/s to 37,3 cm/s, V_{diast} – from 8,3 cm/s to 9,2 cm/s.

Statistical analysis of the results was performed using the Statistica 7 software package, employing descriptive statistics, one-way analysis of variance, and Duncan's post hoc test for multiple comparisons. Differences between compared series were considered significant at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0,05$). Descriptive statistics results in most tables are presented as $M \pm \sigma$, where M is the mean and σ is the standard deviation. The critical level of statistical significance when testing the null hypothesis was set to 0,01, 0,02, and 0,05, depending on the criterion used.

Study results and discussion. In the first group of patients, symptoms of anterior segment damage (conjunctival hyperemia, subconjunctival hemorrhages, and corneal edema), observed during the first day, primarily in association with concomitant trauma, disappeared 14 days after the injury. In the early posttraumatic period, fundus changes were characterized by a decrease in retinal artery caliber (48,7% and 64,7%, respectively) and retinal ischemia (43,4% and 48,8%). With therapy, retinal ischemia resolved in most patients within a week after the injury. By the end of the 3-month follow-up period, ophthalmoscopic fundus examinations in this group of patients returned to normal.

Before the start of complex treatment, visual acuity (VA) in the first group of patients was $0,7 \pm 0,07$.

After the treatment (10 days), we found that in patients of this group, VA increased on average to $0,9 \pm 0,3$ ($p < 0,05$). The obtained data indicate a positive trend in the dynamics of VA in patients, where the VA indicator had a positive effect and stabilization of indicators by the first month of observation - 57% higher than the baseline level, while 3 months after treatment, visual acuity improved by a maximum of 26%.

In patients of the second group, the increase in visual acuity 10 days after treatment was insignificant and amounted to an average of 0,2.

Immediately one month after the end of treatment, VA increased by 0.4. After 3 months of observation, VA and IOP remained stable in patients in this group.

Before treatment, the examined patients showed both a decrease in visual acuity and an increase in visual field defects.

After 10 days, according to perimetry data, improvements in visual fields were noted in 22 eyes of patients in the second group.

According to perimetry data, a significant expansion of the visual fields was observed in 27 eyes of patients in the study group after one month. In five eyes, the visual fields remained unchanged. A decrease in the number of scotomas was observed, with absolute scotomas transitioning to relative scotomas in 14 eyes (43,7%).

After 3 months of observation, visual fields expanded to normal in 9 eyes (28,8%). In 18 eyes (56,3%), visual field boundaries were at baseline.

ultrasound data of the HA before treatment were $19,1 \pm 0,14$ cm/s in the first group of patients. A decrease in the initial level of maximum systolic blood flow velocity (Vs) and an increase in the resistance index RI were revealed in all study groups: a decrease (Vs) in the central artery by 10-35%, in the pericardial osseous carotid artery by 8-26%, and in the HA by 5-23% and an increase in RI in the central artery by up to 10% , in the pericardial osseous carotid artery by up to 7% and in the HA by up to 9%, as well as a decrease in the ischemia coefficient (IC) by 10-13%. In the second group of patients, a decrease in the initial level of maximum systolic blood flow velocity (V) and an increase in the resistance index RI were also revealed: a decrease (Vs) in the central artery by 10-35%, in the pericardial artery by 8-26%, and in the cerebral artery by 5-23% and an increase in RI in the central artery by up to 10% , in the pericardial artery by up to 7% and in the cerebral artery by up to 9%, as well as a decrease in the ischemia coefficient (IC) by 10-13%.

Velocity in the HA in patients of the first group after treatment (10 days) increased to $29,1 \pm 0,21$ cm/s, in the second group it increased to $28,1 \pm 0,17$ cm/s. At 1 month of observation, it was revealed that the blood flow velocity in the HA in the first and second groups was $29,3 \pm 0,17$ and $28,2 \pm 0,11$ cm/s, and after 3 months $26,5 \pm 0,15$ cm/s ($p < 0,05$) and $25,2 \pm 0,11$ cm/s ($p < 0,05$) , respectively.

Thus, treatment effectiveness in both groups was maintained for a long time (3 months). Improved retinal blood flow correlates with visual function indicators and explains their stabilization and improvement.

According to our data, the proposed regimen of drug therapy for TON and GON leads to persistent preservation of visual functions and improvement of hemodynamic parameters (83%).

Conclusions:

1. The detection of a decrease in the LBFV in the CA C ($12,62 \pm 1,21$; $8,83 \pm 0,54$) and PCCA ($12,98 \pm 1,29$; $11,58 \pm 0,86$) indicates a deficiency of blood flow in the retinal and choroidal vessels already in the first day after the injury, which negatively affects the retinal neurons and the optic nerve. The increase in hemodynamic velocity in the GA ($39,38 \pm 4,59$; $37,0 \pm 2,61$) most likely has a compensatory nature of the slowing of hemodynamics of smaller vessels. Complex treatment of patients with zygomatico-orbital injuries should be started early after the injury.

2. The proposed regimen of drug prevention of TON and GON leads to persistent preservation of visual functions and improvement of hemodynamic parameters (83%).

3. Complex treatment is pathogenetically justified, as it reliably improves hemodynamic parameters, reduces the level of chorioretinal ischemia and improves visual acuity within 3 months after treatment.

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